

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Meaningful Misclassifications in Automatic Sound Classification

Suhit Chiruthapudi

Supervisor: Frederic Font

Co-Supervisor: Recep Oğuz Araz

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Abstract

Automatic sound classification systems are increasingly relevant across various fields, from environmental monitoring to creative sound design. While most classification tasks rely on a single ground truth category, this thesis explores the potential value of misclassifications in automatic sound classification, particularly from a sound design perspective. The research investigates whether these misclassifications, often dismissed as errors, could be considered meaningful when they acoustically resemble other categories. By analyzing sound classification performance using different feature extraction models and classifiers within the framework of the Universal Category System (UCS), this study demonstrates that combining semantic and acoustic features leads to improved classification accuracy. The experiments reveal that certain misclassifications might be valuable, suggesting that a flexible, multi-label approach to sound categorization could enhance the utility of sound libraries in creative applications. The findings highlight the importance of considering misclassifications as part of a more nuanced and context-sensitive classification process, offering new possibilities for the future development of automatic sound classification systems.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Motivation	5
1.2	Key Concepts	8
1.2.1	Freesound	8
1.2.2	Taxonomies vs. Ontologies	8
1.2.3	Semantics vs. Acoustic Features	9
1.2.4	Classification Evaluation Metrics	10
1.3	Structure of the Thesis	11
2	State of The Art	12
2.1	Background	12
2.2	Early Efforts in Sound Classification	13
2.2.1	Pitch Perception	13
2.2.2	Timbral Perception	13
2.2.3	Cognitive Psychology based Methods	13
2.3	Later Efforts and the Current Methods in Automatic Sound Classification	14
2.3.1	Machine Learning Models	14
2.3.2	Deep Learning Models and Architectures	16
2.4	Datasets, Taxonomies and Ontologies	17
2.5	Technologies Used	20
2.5.1	The Universal Category System (UCS)	20
2.5.2	Pro Sound Effects Collection	22
2.5.3	Feature Extractors	22
3	Methodology	25
3.1	Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset	25
3.1.1	Dataset and Embeddings Preparation	26
3.1.2	Classification and Evaluation Metrics	28
3.2	Level 2: Evaluation with Multiple Classification Runs	28
3.2.1	Class Filtering	29

3.2.2	Classification and Evaluation Metrics	30
3.2.3	Misclassification Analysis	31
3.2.4	Category ID Analysis	32
3.3	Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset	33
3.3.1	Model Selection, Classification and Evaluation	33
3.3.2	Misclassification Analysis	34
4	Results	35
4.1	Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset	35
4.2	Level 2: Evaluation with Multiple Classification Runs	39
4.2.1	Top Level Category Results	39
4.2.2	Category ID Level Results	45
4.2.3	Misclassification Analysis	47
4.3	Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset	49
5	Discussion	54
5.1	Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset	54
5.2	Level 2: Multiple Classification Runs	55
5.2.1	KNN vs MLP	55
5.2.2	Effect of Category Filters	58
5.2.3	Effect of Category Levels	59
5.2.4	Category ID Confusion Matrices	60
5.2.5	Misclassification Analysis	61
5.3	Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset	63
5.3.1	Comparison with Level 2 Metrics	63
5.3.2	Drop in ‘CHEMICALS’ performance	64
5.3.3	Consistency of Classification over Multiple Runs	65
5.3.4	tSNE Analysis	66
5.4	Future Work	68
6	Conclusion	69
	List of Figures	70
	List of Tables	73
	Bibliography	74
A	Level 2 Experiment Plots	80
A.1	KNN Top Level Categories (Filtered)	80
A.1.1	Category-Wise Accuracy	80

A.1.2	Confusion Matrices	82
A.2	KNN Top Level Categories (Unfiltered)	83
A.2.1	Category-Wise Accuracy	83
A.2.2	Confusion Matrices	84
A.3	MLP Top Level Categories (Filtered)	85
A.3.1	Category-Wise Accuracy	85
A.3.2	Confusion Matrices	86
A.4	MLP Top Level Categories (Unfiltered)	86
A.4.1	Confusion Matrices	86
A.4.2	Category-Wise Accuracy	87
A.5	KNN Category ID Level Confusion Matrices	88
A.5.1	Filtered	88
A.5.2	Unfiltered	89
A.6	MLP Category ID Level Confusion Matrices	90
A.6.1	Filtered	90
A.6.2	Unfiltered	90

Chapter 1

Introduction

The identification of sounds by humans is a complex process influenced by various factors, including context and environment. People also often recognize sounds based on previous experiences, associating certain noises with specific objects, events, or locations. At the moment when a sound is identified or recognised by a human being, the person is effectively conducting a classification of the sound based on all these factors stated above. By weighing and balancing these factors, they are quickly able to identify the sound by its likelihood to exist in that context.

When humans consciously classify sounds, they engage more deeply with the details, moving beyond mere subconscious recognition to actively categorize the sound in a way that best defines it. This classification process can be approached from various perspectives, each offering unique insights into the nature of the sound and its context. For instance, sounds might be categorized by their source, such as a musical instrument, machine, or human voice. Alternatively, they could be classified by location, identifying the environment where the sound originates—whether indoors, outdoors, urban, or natural. Acoustic properties, like frequency, amplitude, pitch, and timbre, provide another rich basis for classification, allowing for distinctions at a more granular level. Time also plays a crucial role, with sounds being categorized based on when they occur, such as during the day or night, or by season. However, using only one of these perspectives rarely gives a well-rounded definition of a sound,

and very often, a combination of these perspectives are used to precisely define a sound.

When the same task is done by a machine, the process is called automatic sound classification. However, for the moment at least, machines do not approach classification the same way as humans do, as it is yet too complex a process for machines to perform. Instead, humans aid the machines by providing examples of sounds and indicating for each example what they would categorise the sound as. Thereafter, using either signal processing techniques, or as is more common now - machine/deep learning techniques, machines can learn from these given examples and then identify new examples with a certain accuracy that is higher than random guessing. But when humans themselves categorise a sound, they are doing so based on their own lived experience so far, as well as their current context and understanding. This means that there is a possibility that two different humans could categorise the same sound slightly differently, and provide two different ‘correct answers’ to the machine during its training. Which answer or perspective is correct? Can both be right? And if so, how can that be explained to a machine?

1.1 Motivation

Sound classification offers significant advantages across a wide range of fields, providing both practical applications and innovative solutions. In sound recognition systems, accurate classification enhances the functionality of voice-activated devices, improving user experience and accessibility [1]. In environmental studies, sound classification is crucial for monitoring ecosystems [2], identifying species through their calls [3], tracking changes in biodiversity [4], and even detecting illegal activities like poaching or deforestation [5]. Medical diagnoses also benefit from advanced sound classification techniques, where subtle acoustic patterns in heartbeats, respiratory sounds, or even vocal tones can be analyzed to detect early signs of illness, offering non-invasive diagnostic tools that can save lives [6, 7, 8]. Additionally, in creative sound design, particularly in industries like film, gaming, and interactive media,

sound classification enables designers to quickly label ¹, search and identify appropriate sounds to accompany visuals or actions, leading to more efficient workflows in the audio post production process [9].

In all of the above fields except for the field of sound design, it is extremely crucial that the sound is accurately identified according to a given ground truth. Therefore, in such fields, it can be presumed that there is always one and only one right answer to a sound's classification. However, in the field of creative sound design, this is not the case. Sound designers very often use one sound to represent an entirely different sound owing to the acoustic similarity of the two. A large part of foley recording and design is based on this understanding. For example, a long, thin metal sheet is struck with a soft mallet to recreate the sound of thunder, or a stick of celery is snapped to recreate the sound of bones breaking. This then poses the question: should the sound be classified as 'bone breaking' or 'celery stick snapping'? And the answer being proposed in this thesis is that both classifications should be considered as being correct from a creative sound design perspective.

In automatic sound classification, a classifier is typically trained using a single ground truth category and is expected to predict a single category as its output. Recent machine learning and deep learning-based audio classification models perform this task by categorizing data points based on underlying patterns and structures within the audio data, as identified through their representative features. During this process, classifiers may occasionally make incorrect classifications or misclassifications relative to the given ground truth category. In most research, these misclassifications are immediately dismissed as errors and are considered to lack value or usefulness.

This thesis, however, argues that these misclassifications might be highly valuable, particularly in the context of sound design. The misclassification likely occurs because of an acoustic and/or semantic similarity between the ground truth category and the predicted category, a principle that sound designers often exploit. For instance, when the exact sound of a source is unavailable, designers recreate the desired

¹<http://hdl.handle.net/10803/296797>

effect using entirely different sound sources that share similar characteristics.

By recognizing such misclassifications as meaningful or sensible and analyzing them in detail — as this thesis will explore — it could become possible to assign multiple category tags to a single audio file. A refined application of this process would allow a file to appear in search queries for all relevant tags (its own ground truth as well as its misclassification), providing sound designers with a broader and more diverse selection of sounds when searching through a sound library. For example, a sound designer searching for a ‘Bone Break’ sound, would expect to get sounds tagged as ‘Celery Snap’ as well if they were meaningfully misclassified as ‘Bone Break’.

This research also has the potential to be of use in the context of Freesound (refer to Section 1.2.1). Freesound allows each user to provide tags to associate with the audio file that they upload onto the website. While the user can submit the tags that they find meaningful, it is often the case that they might only assign tags that describe the sound in terms of its actual source, location, etc. The advantage of meaningful misclassifications in this context is to be able to recommend tags that are acoustically or semantically similar to the uploaded audio file that the user might not have thought of. Considering that Freesound is an important source of free and accessible sound effects for sound designers around the world, such tag recommendations would later be invaluable in helping them sift through thousands of sounds in the repository to find what they need.

The goal of this thesis, therefore, can be divided into two main objectives. The first is to identify a relatively robust combination of audio feature representation, classifier, and categorical structure that can achieve satisfactory automatic classification. The second is to thereafter develop a proof of concept that demonstrates the value of misclassifications in an automatic sound classification task from a sound design perspective.

1.2 Key Concepts

Before proceeding with the next chapters of the thesis, a few key concepts are defined and detailed here, as they are fundamental to the understanding of the propositions put forward by the thesis.

1.2.1 Freesound

Freesound ² is an online platform and collaborative database that offers a vast collection of over 600,000 audio files comprising of sound effects, synthesized sounds and music snippets that users can upload, share, and download freely. It was developed by the Music Technology Group (MTG) at Pompeu Fabra University in Barcelona, Spain. Launched in 2005, Freesound supports creative and educational projects by providing a diverse range of sounds under Creative Commons licenses, allowing for reuse and remixing. The platform employs advanced technologies for sound classification, search, and retrieval, enabling users to find sounds based on tags, descriptions, and even by similarity to other sounds, making it an essential tool for sound designers, musicians, and researchers alike.

1.2.2 Taxonomies vs. Ontologies

Taxonomies are hierarchical structures that classify sounds into nested categories, from broad to specific. For example, a taxonomy for sound might start with general categories like "natural sounds" and "artificial sounds", then branch into more specific subcategories like "animal sounds" or "mechanical sounds" respectively. This straightforward structure makes taxonomies easy to use and navigate, ideal for organising large sound libraries. However, they are limited in capturing complex relationships between sounds, such as how different sounds might be related by context, function, or acoustic properties.

Ontologies, on the other hand, offer a more nuanced approach by mapping not just hierarchical relationships but also the intricate interconnections between different

²<https://freesound.org>

sound categories. In sound classification, an ontology could link sounds not only to their sources but also to their contexts, acoustic properties, and even emotional impact. For instance, it might connect the sound of rain not only to "natural sounds" but also to categories like "calming sounds" or "background noise," depending on its usage in different scenarios. This richer framework is particularly useful in advanced sound classification tasks, where understanding the multifaceted relationships between sounds can create a more robust structure of sound organisation.

1.2.3 Semantics vs. Acoustic Features

Semantics refers to the meaning or context associated with a sound. It involves understanding the sound in terms of the concepts it represents. For instance, in sound classification, semantics might involve recognizing that a particular sound represents a "car horn" or "birdsong," and understanding its role or function in a specific environment, like "urban traffic" or "natural habitat." Semantics helps in linking sounds to their real-world applications or contexts, enabling more intuitive and meaningful categorisation. For example, classifying sounds based on their source or the action they represent, such as "alarm" or "water dripping," reflects semantic understanding. This approach is particularly useful for applications that require a deeper understanding of how sounds are used or perceived in various contexts, such as in sound design and environmental monitoring.

Acoustic features, on the other hand, pertain to the physical properties of the sound itself. These include measurable attributes such as frequency, amplitude, pitch, timbre, and duration. Acoustic features are derived from the waveform of the sound and are used to characterize its technical aspects. For instance, features like spectral centroid, mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs), and zero-crossing rate are commonly used in machine learning models to analyze and classify sounds based on their intrinsic properties. Acoustic features are essential for tasks that involve the technical analysis of sound, such as speech recognition, music genre classification, and audio signal processing. They provide a quantitative basis for distinguishing between different sounds based on their physical characteristics rather than their

meanings.

1.2.4 Classification Evaluation Metrics

In evaluating classification models, several key metrics are commonly used to assess performance.

Accuracy

Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly predicted instances out of the total, offering a simple gauge of overall performance, though it may be misleading in imbalanced datasets.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{No. of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total no. of Predictions}}$$

F1 Score

The F1 Score, which is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, provides a more balanced evaluation by considering both false positives and false negatives, making it particularly useful in cases of class imbalance. Precision measures how many of the predicted positive instances are actually positive, whereas Recall (or Sensitivity or True Positive Rate) measures how many of the actual positive instances the model correctly identified.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Confusion Matrix

A Confusion Matrix offers a visual, detailed breakdown of model performance by showing the counts or strengths of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives in a 2-dimensional grid. The categories are arranged along both axes in a manner that aligns each category's reference to itself on the opposite axis, forming a diagonal line from the top left to the bottom right of the grid.

AUR-ROC Score

Lastly, the AUR-ROC Score (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve) assesses a model's ability to distinguish between classes across different threshold settings. It represents the probability that a randomly chosen positive instance is ranked higher by the classifier than a randomly chosen negative instance. Thus, a higher AUR-ROC value indicates a better performing model.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 2: State of the Art - discusses the history of automatic sound classification as well as present practices. At the same time, the technologies and categorisation structures used in this thesis are presented in detail.

Chapter 3: Methodology - provides a step-by-step breakdown of how the experiments for this study were conducted and gives the rationale for those steps.

Chapter 4: Results - presents the results that were derived from the experiments and highlights some significant features in the findings.

Chapter 5: Discussion - Analyses the results derived from the experiment in detail, while suggesting possible explanations for the results. It also brings to attention possible emerging patterns from these findings.

Chapter 6: Conclusion - finally provides an overview of the analysis derived from this thesis.

Chapter 2

State of The Art

2.1 Background

Sound classification involves the task of automatically identifying the category or characteristics of a sound signal. This can range from recognizing spoken words in speech recognition to identifying the genre of a piece of music or detecting environmental sounds like footsteps, bird calls, or car horns. This task finds applications in various fields such as wildlife monitoring, urban planning, virtual assistant interactions, personalized music recommendations, security monitoring systems, medical analysis/diagnosis, among others.

Automatic sound classification, the process of categorising audio signals into pre-defined classes using computational techniques, has seen significant advancements over the years. The formal beginnings of systematic efforts to classify sounds using computational methods can be traced back to the parallel development of computational techniques and the study of acoustics. The following sections provide an overview of the key developments in the field, from early beginnings to the current state-of-the-art approaches.

2.2 Early Efforts in Sound Classification

Early attempts at sound categorisation based on psychological and psychoacoustic principles were foundational in shaping the field of automatic sound classification. These efforts focused on understanding how humans perceive and categorise sounds, with the goal of developing computational models that mimic these processes. While a lot of these studies did not attempt to categorise sounds according to large taxonomical structures, they attempted to recognise the features that allowed human beings to perceive one sound to be different from another, and could therefore categorise the two sounds differently.

2.2.1 Pitch Perception

The perception of pitch related information was a central focus of early sound categorisation research. Helmholtz's place theory [10] proposed that different frequencies stimulate different regions along the basilar membrane of the cochlea, leading to the perception of pitch. Terhardt's harmonic template model [11] proposed that the auditory system recognizes pitch by comparing incoming sounds to a template of harmonic frequencies.

2.2.2 Timbral Perception

Risset and Chowning developed computational models [12, 13] based on the analysis of the spectral envelope of sounds, aiming to capture the unique timbral characteristics of different instruments, and thereby categorize them using those characteristics.

2.2.3 Cognitive Psychology based Methods

In the realm of cognitive psychology, researchers like Max Wertheimer, Eleanor Rosch and others developed theories of categorization that applied to various sensory modalities, including auditory perception.

Gestalt psychology's principles, put forward by Wertheimer [14], focus on how humans perceive and organize complex visual stimuli into meaningful patterns, but

these principles can also be applied to organise sounds into categories. As a particular example of the proximity principle, humans could possibly tend to group the sounds of birds chirping, rustling of grass, wind and children playing into a single environment of a ‘park’, ‘lawn’, ‘field’, etc.

Rosch’s prototype theory [15] suggests that humans categorize objects based on their resemblance to a prototype or central example of a category. A clear example of this form of categorisation is in the formation and establishment of musical genres. Rosch’s theory suggests that humans form mental prototypes or ideal representations of genres, and they then classify new instances based on their resemblance to these genres.

Similarly, the concept of Auditory Scene Analysis was introduced by Bergman [16]. It refers to the process by which humans perceptually organize complex auditory scenes into meaningful perceptual objects by focusing on principles such as auditory grouping, segregation, and integration, which are fundamental to how humans make sense of auditory input. These principles laid the groundwork for computational models of sound segregation, where algorithms attempt to separate sounds from a mixture based on perceptual cues like pitch, timbre, and spatial location.

Additionally, Ballas conducted experiments based on psychoacoustic principles to determine a mix of acoustic, ecological, perceptual and cognitive factors that are common in the identification of 41 brief, varied sounds [17].

2.3 Later Efforts and the Current Methods in Automatic Sound Classification

2.3.1 Machine Learning Models

Before the advent of deep learning, sound classification relied heavily on manually engineered features like Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) [18]. These features, derived from audio signals through a series of transformations mimicking human auditory perception, served as the foundation for traditional machine learn-

ing models such as Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs).

Hidden Markov models (HMMs) were often used in early automatic classification tasks for modeling temporal dependencies in audio sequences. Couvreur et al. [19] demonstrated how HMMs can be used to build an environmental noise recognition system based on a time-frequency analysis of the noise signal that was able to outperform the average human listener. Baumann et al. [20] employed features describing level fluctuations, the spectral form and harmonicity to distinguish between the four sound classes ‘clean speech’, ‘speech in noise’, ‘noise’, and ‘music’ using hidden Markov models.

Support vector machines (SVMs) were also commonly used for the task of audio classification due to their ability to handle high-dimensional feature spaces. Lie et al. [21] utilised SVMs in order to classify segments from a stream of sound into classes of silence, music, background sound, pure speech, and non-pure speech. Chien-Chang et al. [22] applied wavelets to extract acoustical features such as sub-band power and pitch information. Along with additional features such as frequency cepstral coefficients, they too used a support vector machine to classify sounds in the MuscleFish dataset ¹. Chen et al. [23] also used SVMs for the classification of mixed type audio data, such as clips having speech with music as background.

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) were employed for modeling audio feature distributions as they provide a probabilistic framework for classification tasks. Bahoura et al. [24] utilised cepstral analysis along with GMMs to classify respiratory sounds into two categories of breathing and wheezing. Roch et al. [25] were able to classify the vocalisations of four free-ranging delphinid species using GMMs.

It was also common to use a GMM-HMM hybrid for classification tasks as they often performed better than individual machine learning methods, as demonstrated by Rajapakse et al. [26].

¹<https://www.cs.princeton.edu/courses/archive/spr99/cs598b/musclefish.html>

2.3.2 Deep Learning Models and Architectures

In recent years, the advent of deep learning techniques has resulted in the possibility of allowing machines to identify and extract significant features from audio that would allow it to successfully classify sounds. The features are multi-dimensional representations of audio characteristics that are not necessarily understandable to humans, and yet often seem to outperform humans at sound classification tasks.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been very popular for this form of representational learning as demonstrated by Hershey et al. [27], Salamon et al. [28] and Piczak [29]. A CNN works by processing sound data through a series of convolutional layers designed to extract relevant features. Initially, the sound data is represented as a spectrogram, which is then passed through the convolutional layers. These layers apply filters/kernels to the spectrogram, learning to recognize patterns and features at different scales. After each convolutional layer, the dimensionality of the data is reduced, which makes the network more computationally efficient, and also allows the model to generalise features for broader cases. The output of the CNN would be the feature-representation of the audio data. These representations are then fed to a neural network usually consisting of a couple of dense layers in order for them to be classified according to the given labels.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) excel in modeling temporal dependencies in audio sequences as they are effective in capturing long-term context and sequential patterns in audio data. They are thus often used in combination with CNNs to amplify their efficacy in sound classification tasks as shown by Bae et al. [30], Bubashait et al. [31], and Bahmei et al. [32].

There have also been attempts to encode features without the use of CNNs. Gong et al. [33] and Chen et al. [34] use an attention based transformer model in order to extract embeddings that are then used for the task of sound classification.

All the methods stated above are used to extract representations of the audio data, which are trained alongside single class target labels under supervised learning.

This immediately necessitates the need for an organised structure of storing sounds in a database, and there have therefore been numerous contributions from various researchers and institutions to create taxonomies and ontologies of sound categorisation. Some of the popular and commonly used taxonomies are detailed in the following section.

2.4 Datasets, Taxonomies and Ontologies

One of the earliest documented collection of catalogued sounds is the BBC Sound Effects library, which contains 23 sound categories into which all the 33,066 sounds in the library - collected over multiple decades leading up to the year 2000 - are divided. The taxonomy is categorized by type and context, such as animals, weather, human activities, etc. ²

Thereafter, there were multiple datasets created that catered to more specific subsets and tasks of audio classification. Garofolo et al. put together the TIMIT Acoustic-phonetic Continuous Speech Corpus [35] in 1992, which contains recordings of 630 speakers of eight major dialects of American English, for use in speech recognition tasks. Later, in 2000, Pearce et al. designed the AURORA dataset [36] for evaluating speech recognition algorithms in noisy conditions. In 2002, Tzanetakis and Cook created the GTZAN music genre classification dataset [37] containing 100 thirty second samples in each of the following ten musical genres: Blues, Classical, Country, Disco, Hip Hop, Jazz, Metal, Popular, Reggae, and Rock.

With research focusing mostly on speech and music processing in auditory recognition tasks, coupled with the rapid expansion of machine learning in the 2010s, the demand for large datasets centered on environmental sounds — and thus encompassing a broader range of sounds — became increasingly important. Salamon et al. created the UrbanSound dataset [38] containing 27 hours of audio (collected from Freesound) with 18.5 hours of annotated sound event occurrences across 10 sound classes. They also proposed the Urbansound taxonomy which starts with a broad top-level categorisation into Human, Mechanical, Nature and Music sounds,

²<https://sound-effects.bbcrewind.co.uk>

and then further divides into lower level sound categories. However, despite the size of the dataset provided, the presence of only 10 classes allowed for only a limited possibility into the study of automatic sound classification and to find meaningful insights into their misclassifications.

Figure 1: Overview of the UrbanSound Taxonomy

The ESC-50 dataset, developed by Karol J. Piczak [39], on the other hand contains 50 equally distributed sound classes from 2000 sounds (collected from Freesound), each of which are 5 seconds long. The 50 sound classes fall under 5 loosely defined major categories: animal sounds, natural soundscapes and water sounds, human (non-speech) sounds, interior/domestic sounds and exterior/urban sounds. Although this dataset contains 50 sound classes, each class represents very specific objects/events/actions and the taxonomy used is too specific to be able to cover a large number of commonly used sound categories in sound design such as cloth, bicycles, etc.

As an alternative to using a taxonomical structure to organise sound files, Font et al. [40] study the user-sourced tags for sounds in Freesound to analyse the folksonomy that emerges from such multiple tags that are associated with each sound file. This structure reflects a more relevant way of organising sound files from a sound design perspective, as it not only tends to provide more context to the content of the sound file, but also allows for the sound to be associated with various interpretations of its acoustic quality. However, as pointed out in the same paper, such a user-driven

structure lends itself to noisy data in terms of incorrect or inconsistent tags being applied to a sound, making it difficult to extract structured information from the folksonomy.

Another dataset that utilised manual annotation of an existing sound base (in this case, Youtube) was the Audioset Ontology, developed by Gemmeke et al. [41]. But instead of associating multiple tags with a sound file, this dataset follows a hierarchical ontology of 632 sound categories with a maximum depth of 6 levels in the hierarchy. The official release of the dataset, however, comes with pre-computed audio features of 10-second long segments of audios from various Youtube videos, and although it also provides the url to the Youtube video that each sound belongs to, it reduces the flexibility and ease of access to work directly with the audio.

Figure 2: First Two Layers of the Audioset Ontology

Addressing these limitations mentioned above, Foncesca et al. developed the open FSD-50K dataset [42] through the manual annotation of 100 hours of sounds, com-

prising over 51,000 audio clips from Freesound. The sounds were categorised into 200 classes derived from the Audioset ontology.

Although the above taxonomies and ontologies present a range of audio categorisation structures, there are many more in existence. As can be seen from the above discussion that there is no single taxonomy or ontology that is used by all the existing datasets, which poses various problems related to the lack of consistency in categorisation across datasets, disagreements in the rules that determine how a sound is to be classified, as well as efficient and comparable evaluation of classification models across datasets.

2.5 Technologies Used

The following section details the various technologies that were used in this research work. This includes the taxonomy, the sound effects library, and various feature extractors that are essential to conduct the experiments proposed by this research.

2.5.1 The Universal Category System (UCS)

The Universal Category System ³ is a framework developed for creating a standardised, exhaustive taxonomy for the purpose of classifying sound effects. It was created by sound designers and editors working in collaboration with sound effects library companies in order to establish a single taxonomical structure that all libraries can thereafter follow.

The UCS therefore offers a standardised set of categories that are hierarchically structured into three levels as follows:

1. Top Level Categories: These are the broadest form of categories that occupy the highest level of the taxonomical structure. There are 82 unique top level categories, and each of them represent a noun such as ‘TOY’, ‘FIRE’, ‘AIR’, etc.

³<https://universalcategorysystem.com>

2. Sub Categories: These categories form the second level of the taxonomical structure, and are 288 in number. These categories help to describe the top level categories, and they usually take the form of adjectives, verbs or nouns such as ‘Mechanical’, ‘Handling’, ‘Movement’, etc. They are therefore shared by the top level categories and are not unique. For example, the sub category ‘Movement’ can be shared by both the top level categories - ‘CLOTH’ and ‘PLASTIC’.
3. Category Id: These are the most specific level of categories in the taxonomy, and are essentially the unique combination of a top level category with a sub category, e.g. ‘PLASTIC’ and ‘Movement’ from the top level category and sub category respectively combine to form the category id, ‘PLASMvmt’. There are a total of 457 such unique category ids in the taxonomy.

Category	SubCategory	CatID
AIR	BLOW	AIRBlow
AIR	BURST	AIRBrst
AIR	HISS	AIRHiss
AIR	MISC	AIRMisc
AIR	SUCTION	AIRSuck
AIRCRAFT	DOOR	AERODoor
AIRCRAFT	HELICOPTER	AEROHeli
AIRCRAFT	INTERIOR	AEROInt
AIRCRAFT	JET	AEROJet
AIRCRAFT	MECHANISM	AEROMech
AIRCRAFT	MILITARY	AEROMil
AIRCRAFT	MISC	AEROMisc
AIRCRAFT	PROP	AEROProp
AIRCRAFT	RADIO CONTROLLED	AERORadio
AIRCRAFT	ROCKET	AERORckt
ALARMS	BELL	ALRMBell
ALARMS	BUZZER	ALRMBuzr
ALARMS	CLOCK	ALRMClok
ALARMS	ELECTRONIC	ALRMElec
ALARMS	MISC	ALRMMisc
ALARMS	SIREN	ALRMSirn
AMBIENCE	AIR	AMBAir
AMBIENCE	ALPINE	AMBAlpn
AMBIENCE	AMUSEMENT	AMBAmus
AMBIENCE	BIRDSONG	AMBBird
AMBIENCE	CELEBRATION	AMBCele
AMBIENCE	CONSTRUCTION	AMBCnst
AMBIENCE	DESERT	AMBDsrt

Figure 3: Example of Universal Category System’s Taxonomical Structure

With this taxonomy, the UCS aims to be future proof by covering all possible categories that could exist for a sound. It does so by using slightly vague top level categories such as ‘OBJECTS’ or ‘ARCHIVED’, and generic sub categories like ‘Miscellaneous’. The usefulness of slightly ambiguous categories such as these will

be discussed later in this thesis. As this thesis aims to study automatic sound classification from the sound designer's perspective, and as the UCS aims to standardise present and future sound effect taxonomies, it is therefore important to consider and analyse the performance of classifiers working within this taxonomical framework.

2.5.2 Pro Sound Effects Collection

Pro Sound Effects (PSE)⁴ bundle is a company that provides large collections of high quality audio sound effects that is used extensively by audio, film, television, gaming and multimedia professionals across the world. Pro Sound Effects provides sound effects bundles of various sizes (in terms of the number of audio files the collection contains). All the sounds within the bundle provided to the Music Technology Group at Pompeu Fabra University (numbering more than 380,000 sound files) have already been categorised according to the Universal Category System (UCS). A .xlsx file was also provided along with the sound files within which each sound file in the bundle is mapped to a corresponding Top Level Category, Sub Category and Category id. The category labels provided in this .xlsx file are used to train and evaluate the classifier models used in this research.

While there are more than 380,000 audio files available, approximately 143,000 audio files were used for this study. A subset of these 143,000 files (comprising of 5568 audio files) was also initially used in this study to perform a preliminary comparative analysis of the automatic classification process between different pre-computed feature sets (which will be discussed in the following subsection). The detailed preparation of the dataset for the purpose of this research is later discussed in the Methodology Section.

2.5.3 Feature Extractors

The representative features of each audio file in the PSE dataset were extracted using four different methods and models, each of which are detailed below:

⁴<https://www.prosoundeffects.com>

1. **Freesound Extractor:** The Freesound Extractor is an algorithm provided by Essentia - an open-source library of tools for audio and music analysis, description and synthesis⁵. The algorithm extracts a large set of acoustic features of a given batch of audio files. These features consist of spectral, time-domain, rhythm and tonal characteristics of the given audio files.
2. **FSD-SINET:** The Freesound Shift-Invariance Network (FSD-SINET) model is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based embedding extractor [43]. It takes a 2D image of the audio file's spectrogram as the input and provides an output embedding vector of size 512. It was trained using audio files from the FSD-50k dataset.
3. **CLAP:** The Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining Model developed by Elizalde et al. [44] uses both the audio signal and a semantic description of the sound as inputs to create vector representations that exist in a joint embedding space which is capable of capturing both acoustic and semantic representations of an audio file. It does this by first creating separate embedding spaces for encoding the audio information and the semantic information respectively. For the pre-training process, the semantic information that is introduced to the semantic encoder branch can take the form of phrases such as, '*A camp fire crackles as the flames burn branches and leaves.*' Meanwhile the audio encoder branch is given the audio file to which the above caption was assigned. Within this pre-training procedure, it also aligns the two spaces into one combined embedding space through the process of contrastive learning. The penultimate layer (a vector of size 512) of the output of this trained network is taken as the feature representation of the audio file, which contains both acoustic and semantic information. CLAP uses audio files from 4 datasets as part of its training process: FSD-50k, ClothoV2 [45], AudioCaps [46] and MACS [47].
4. **LAION-CLAP:** The LAION-CLAP model, developed by Wu et al. [48] is very similar to the previous CLAP model. It however uses a different dataset

⁵<https://essentia.upf.edu>

- LAION-Audio-630K ⁶ - with different audio and text encoders in the pre-training process, and is also able to handle audio files of varying lengths.

The four feature extractor models detailed above have been selected in order to perform a comparative analysis of the classification task based on the kind of features that the classifier is being fed. This comparative analysis will provide insights into the performance of human understandable acoustic features (Freesound Extractor), against deep features extracted from spectrograms through a CNN (FSD-SINET), as well as combined semantic-acoustic embeddings through large neural networks (CLAP, LAION-CLAP). The comparison between the CLAP and LAION-CLAP models will further allow one to identify the impact of varying datasets and encoders in their respective semantic-acoustic embeddings' performance.

As mentioned earlier, the Pro Sound Effects bundle provided to the Music Technology Group consists of over 380,000 sounds. However, out of these sounds, the embeddings of approximately 143,000 sounds have already been extracted using the FSD-SINET, CLAP and LAION-CLAP models by Recep Oğuz Araz for his Masters Thesis research work [49]. This research work uses these embeddings for its analysis, as it can be argued that this is more than a sufficient amount of data for the purpose of its study. However, the acoustic features of the sounds from the dataset were extracted using Freesound Extractor during the course of the research.

⁶<https://github.com/LAION-AI/audio-dataset/>

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter outlines the experimental design and methods used to evaluate the performance of the classification task on the Universal Category System. For the sake of simplicity, the approximately 143,000 sounds that have pre-computed embeddings will be referred to as the Pro Sound Effects dataset for the remainder of this thesis. As this dataset is quite large in number and working with such a number will require a lot of computational power, the experiments are broken down and conducted at three distinct levels for the sake of computational efficiency, each progressively increasing in dataset size finally to the entire 143,000 sounds, or in complexity and depth of analysis, while reducing larger experimental variables such as feature extractor & classifier model combinations. The aim is to thoroughly investigate the performance of the classifiers and feature extractors, and understand the nature of misclassifications.

3.1 Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset

The first level of experimentation focuses on conducting a preliminary evaluation of two classifiers - K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) - on the subset of the dataset, using embeddings from each of the four feature extractors. This stage is intended to establish baseline performance metrics and to observe how each classifier handles the data with different feature extractors.

3.1.1 Dataset and Embeddings Preparation

In order to allow for a rapid initial evaluation of the classification process, a representative subset of the Pro Sound Effects dataset was used. This subset consists of 7990 sounds and is balanced similar to the entire dataset across Top Level Categories (TLCs).

The 7990 file names of the subset (without the file extension) were checked for matches with the file names of the previously extracted embeddings of the FSD-SINET, CLAP and LAION-CLAP models in order to identify missing embeddings. It was found that out of 7990 audio files in the subset, embeddings were available for 5568 audio files, so the embeddings for these 5568 sound files were used for this analysis. It is to be noted that this step affects the distribution of the categories, and could therefore not be entirely representative of the larger dataset. However, checks were made to verify that the distribution across categories is not heavily skewed, as will be discussed later.

The acoustic features of all the 7990 sound files were extracted using Freesound extractor. Out of all the acoustic features extracted, only the low-level features were retained for the analysis, as higher-level features such as rhythmic and tonal features such as tempo, chord information, etc. were considered to be largely irrelevant to the features of sound effects. While higher-level features such as periodicity and inharmonicity can be argued to be potentially significant in understanding sound effects, it is assumed that the lower-level features can sufficiently capture the information that would represent these higher-level features. The verification of this assumption, however, is currently beyond the scope of this Masters thesis work, due to time considerations.

As some of the low-level features of each audio file contain frame level information, it was decided to use statistical methods to create clip level representations of those features similar to the methodology used by [49]. Statistical values such as the mean and variance of such features were computed, along with the first and second derivatives of the mean and variance. This ensured that all the acoustic features of

each audio file were aggregated, clip-level features. There were a total of 846 clip level features for each audio file. In order to make the analysis less computationally intensive, Min-Max scaling and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to the 846 features to reduce each audio file’s feature vector to a size of 100, while retaining the most significant features.

As the distribution of the subset of the selected 5568 files was imbalanced across categories, it was important to ensure that sufficient number of audio files remained in each category for the classification training process. Therefore, only those categories were selected that contained at least 30 audio files, guaranteeing a satisfactory train and validation split. By conducting this process, there were a total of 5437 audio files and 74 top level categories remaining for the training process. Table 1 below provides an overview of the discussion presented above.

Table 1: Analysis of available embeddings

Condition	Count
Total no. of pre-computed embeddings	143314
Total no. of audio files in PSE subset	7990
Total no. of audio files with pre-computed embeddings	5568
Total no. of audio files selected for Level 1	5437

The embeddings for these 5437 audio files that were common to each of the four feature extractors were then split into train and validation sets at a ratio of 80:20, using a stratified split which ensured that the audio files from each top level category would be split in the 80:20 ratio. This ensures that data from each category is represented in the training process, which would not be the case if the 5437 audio files were randomly split into an 80:20 ratio. The train-validation split was performed within the audio files, and therefore each feature extractor contained the same train-validation sets of computed embeddings as each other, thereby making certain that the downstream classifier saw the same training and validation splits of data from each feature extractor.

3.1.2 Classification and Evaluation Metrics

The training set embeddings of each of the four feature extractors were fed separately into a k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) classifier and a Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP) for the training phase. The number of Nearest Neighbours in the KNN classifier was set at 3. The MLP classifier had a depth of two hidden layers, with 300 and 150 neurons in the first and second hidden layers, followed by 74 neurons in the output layer for the 74 top level categories. These parameters were arrived at through a hyperparameter optimisation process that involved running the data through these classifiers with varying parameters (such as number of nearest neighbours, and hidden layer sizes) to find the least computationally expensive parameters that achieved the best accuracy. Therefore, with four feature extractor models and two classifiers, there were a total of eight unique extractor-classifier models.

With the completion of the training phase, the validation set was passed through each of the eight extractor-classifier models, to evaluate their respective performance. For the sake of evaluation, common classification metrics such as accuracy, F1 score, AUC score and a confusion matrix were computed for each of the eight combinations.

Finally, the filenames of misclassified audio files were noted along with their respective predicted and ground truth categories. Out of this set of misclassified audio files, ten audio files were randomly selected for each extractor-classifier combination, in order to manually listen to them and aurally verify if the predicted class (considered incorrect with respect to the ground truth) makes acoustic sense.

3.2 Level 2: Evaluation with Multiple Classification Runs

The second level of experimentation builds upon the initial analysis by conducting multiple runs of the eight extractor-classifier combinations on the dataset subset. By conducting multiple runs of the classification, this phase introduces variability in the train-validation splits, and by taking the average of an extractor-classifier's perfor-

mance over multiple iterations, accounts for small changes in the evaluation metrics related to a specific train-validation split. This level also explores the impact of filtering certain classes from the dataset on the performance of the classification task. Finally, this entire process is carried out by replacing the top level category with the category ID as the target category, and the performance is similarly evaluated across all extractor-classifier combinations.

3.2.1 Class Filtering

The Universal Category System (UCS) contains certain top level categories such as ‘ARCHIVED’, ‘EQUIPMENT’, ‘OBJECTS’, etc. as well as sub categories such as ‘MISC’, which introduce a fair amount of ambiguity in the semantic representation of such categories. Various sounds within such characteristics often bear no acoustic resemblance to each other as well. For example, the ‘OBJECTS’ category contains sounds of interactions with a soap bottle dispenser’s lid, or a cardboard pipe, or a metal wire, etc. All of these have no semantic nor acoustic relation to each other, and thus one can argue that such sounds being grouped together into one category introduces ambiguity to what that category represents. Such ambiguity could therefore have the potential to affect the classifier’s performance, and also raises the question whether it makes sense to introduce such a category to an automatic sound classification task, when even human beings would find it difficult to clearly define such a category.

The hypothesis being presented, therefore, is that filtering out such classes should clearly improve the performance of the classifiers. In order to test this hypothesis, one more variable was added to the second level of the experiment. Each extractor-classifier combination model was trained and evaluated with and without the filtering of such ambiguous categories. The top level categories that were filtered out were: ‘ARCHIVED’, ‘SPORTS’, ‘CARTOON’, ‘EQUIPMENT’, ‘TOYS’, ‘OBJECTS’. The ‘ARCHIVED’ top level category consists of sounds of various tone sweeps and impulse responses in different locations, whereas the ‘SPORTS’ category consists of a large variety of sports, being played in different locations and

environments at different times of day. The ‘CARTOON’, ‘EQUIPMENT’, ‘TOYS’ and ‘OBJECTS’ categories, similarly, contain too acoustically diverse a collection of sounds, in order for them to make sense as a category that can be represented clearly, and were all therefore, filtered out. There was only one sub category that was filtered out, and that was ‘MISC’. This meant that any sound in the subset of the dataset that was annotated with any of these top level categories or sub category was not considered for the experiment. On applying this filter, there were a total of 4355 audio files that remained. In addition, similar to the first level experiment, only the categories that contained at least 30 audio files in the subset were retained. Finally, as shown in Table 2, with the category filter applied, there were 4111 audio files and 62 categories available for the experiment, while without the application of the category filter, there were 5437 audio files and 74 categories that remained (which is the same number as seen in Table 1 in the initial dataset evaluation).

Table 2: No. of top level categories and audio files with/without filtering

Category Filter	No. of Categories	No. of Audio Files
Unfiltered	74	5437
Filtered	62	4111

3.2.2 Classification and Evaluation Metrics

Considering the three experimental variables (Feature Extractor type, Classifier type, category filter vs. no category filter) that are present in the second level of the methodology, there are sixteen unique extractor-classifier-filter combinations that are evaluated at this stage.

While the architecture of the KNN classifier remains the same as the previous level, the MLP has a slight modification to the sizes of the hidden layers based on whether the category filter is applied or not. The sizes of the first and second hidden layers take four times and two times the number of available Top Level Categories respectively, as shown below.

Size of Hidden Layer 1 = $4 \times$ No. of Top Level Categories

Size of Hidden Layer 2 = $2 \times$ No. of Top Level Categories

These values were arrived at by finding the best performing integer multiplier with respect to the number of TLCs, upon running multiple iterations of the MLP classification with various hidden layer sizes.

The training set was processed through a KNN classifier for 50 iterations and an MLP classifier for 30 iterations. In each iteration, a new stratified train-validation split was created to ensure the classifier encountered differently sampled data during each training phase. Accuracy, F1 score, AUC score, and the confusion matrix were recorded for each iteration. Additionally, by analyzing the misclassifications in each run, the category-wise accuracy was calculated and stored. The average accuracy across all categories was then computed at the end of each iteration, yielding the balanced accuracy for that iteration. This balanced accuracy is necessary because the dataset is imbalanced across categories, meaning that a larger number of data points in a specific category could potentially distort the model's perceived accuracy.

After the completion of all the iterations of the classification process, the accuracy, balanced accuracy, F1 score, AUC score, confusion matrix, and category-wise accuracies from each iteration were collected. The arithmetic means of these metrics across all iterations were then calculated to represent the overall performance of the extractor-classifier-filter combination.

3.2.3 Misclassification Analysis

Finally, the misclassifications from these multiple runs were analyzed in greater detail. The best-performing model under the optimal filtering conditions was selected, and 100 random misclassifications were listened to and manually evaluated. The objective was to determine how many of these misclassifications were "sensible" from the context of a sound designer searching for the predicted category. For instance, a sensible misclassification might occur when the audio file sounds like its predicted

category, which is not the ground truth category as provided by the dataset. For example, an audio file of a cloth flapping in the wind and classified in the dataset as CLOTH might be misclassified as WINGS, which is a sensible prediction, especially when considering that a lot of foley artists themselves recreate the sound of birds' wings by flapping a piece of cloth. By listening to the 100 random misclassifications, a count of sensible misclassifications out of 100 was made.

As an initial proof of concept, this study proposes to consider this count of sensible misclassifications as valid and correct classifications. On doing so, this count can represent an accuracy of sensible misclassifications. This can then be added to the overall accuracy of the extractor-classifier-filter model to give a more representative accuracy from the sound design perspective.

3.2.4 Category ID Analysis

The entire methodology followed in this level of experiments was repeated by taking the Category ID as the target category for each extractor-classifier-filter model to predict. As there are far more category IDs than top level categories in the dataset, the total number of audio files within each category ID are far fewer than what were available in each top level category. For this reason, the minimum required audio files per category ID was relaxed to allow those category IDs that contained at least 10 audio files, as opposed to the requirement of 30 audio files for each top level category. Table 3 summarizes the number of audio files and category IDs available with respect to the filter being applied.

Table 3: No. of category IDs and audio files with/without filtering

Category Filter	No. of Categories	No. of Audio Files
Unfiltered	156	4317
Filtered	120	3457

3.3 Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset

The final level of experimentation involves a comprehensive evaluation of the extractor-classifier-filter model that performed best in the previous levels. This evaluation uses the entire Pro Sound Effects dataset consisting of over 143,000 sounds (of which embeddings were computed) and collects the previously defined metrics for a top level category analysis. It also aims to briefly study if the arrangement of the embeddings in the embedding space can provide an insight into the sensible misclassifications that occur in the classification process.

3.3.1 Model Selection, Classification and Evaluation

Given the large dataset at this stage of the analysis, the extractor-classifier model that achieved the highest AUC score in the previous round of experiments was selected as the sole model for the classification task at this level. The previous results provided a representative picture of the best-performing model, making it unnecessary to continue comparative analysis with other models on such a large dataset. The AUC score was chosen as the decisive metric because the study focuses on the classifier's ability to effectively distinguish between classes, which the AUC score best represents. Moreover, while accuracy is typically calculated based on the assumption that the ground truth category is the only correct category for classification, this study acknowledges that many misclassifications might be meaningful from a sound design perspective.

Initially, a 2-dimensional t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (tSNE) was computed using all the embeddings in the dataset (see subsection 3.3.2 below). The classification process and metric evaluation at this stage followed the same procedure as in the previous level: multiple iterations were run, metrics were calculated for each iteration, and the results were averaged after all iterations were completed. Additionally, the five categories with the lowest accuracy were identified, and one of these categories was randomly chosen for further investigation, as outlined below.

3.3.2 Misclassification Analysis

For the selected category out of the five lowest performing ones, the metrics were analyzed to identify the category it was most often misclassified as during the classification process. The audio files predicted as belonging to this most frequently misclassified category were then marked and stored. Subsequently, a 2-dimensional tSNE scatter plot was generated, displaying only the embeddings of the low-accuracy category and its most misclassified counterpart in two different colors, with the previously marked audio files highlighted in a third color. This plot was visually examined for patterns that could explain the sensible misclassifications. Further discussion of these findings will be presented in the Results and Discussion section.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the results of the experiments that were conducted, as detailed in the Methodology section above. The results are divided into three sections, corresponding to the three levels of experimentation that were carried out. The metrics of Accuracy, Balanced Accuracy, F1 score, AUR-ROC score and confusion matrices are employed for the evaluation of the experiments.

4.1 Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset

The objective of the first level of experimentation was to conduct a preliminary comparative analysis of the classifiers and feature extractors in the classification process on the subset of the dataset. The study was carried out with top level categories and consisted of 74 categories in total.

Accuracy: During a single run of the train-validation set through both classifiers, it was observed that the feature extractors combining semantic and acoustic embeddings (CLAP and LAION-CLAP) outperformed the other two extractors in terms of accuracy. In contrast, the Freesound extractor, which relies on low-level acoustic descriptors, demonstrated the lowest accuracy.

Both the KNN and MLP classifiers performed equally well with the CLAP and LAION-CLAP models. However, the MLP classifier showed better classification

performance with the FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models. The accuracy of each feature extractor for both classifiers is illustrated in Figure 4.

F1 Score: The F1 score exhibited a similar trend to accuracy across the feature extractors, with the MLP classifier achieving a higher F1 score than the KNN classifier when using the FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models, as can be seen in Figure 5.

AUR-ROC Score: Figure 6 shows a clear difference in the performance between KNN and MLP classifiers with respect to the AUR-ROC score, with the MLP classifier outperforming the KNN classifier across all feature extractor models.

Figure 4: Classification Accuracy of each Feature Extractor and Classifier

Figure 5: Classification F1 Score of each Feature Extractor and Classifier

Figure 6: Classification AUC Score of each Feature Extractor and Classifier

Confusion Matrices The confusion matrices of the four feature extractors with an MLP classifier are shown in Figure 7. From the plots, it can be seen that all the four

4.2 Level 2: Evaluation with Multiple Classification Runs

As observed in the level 1 experiments, the CLAP and LAION-CLAP models demonstrated nearly identical performance metrics. However, for a more reliable evaluation, it is important to assess all the feature extractors' performances across multiple classification runs with different train-validation splits. Additionally, the impact of applying category filters to the dataset is presented here, with the results organized by the dataset's two category levels: top-level categories (TLC) and category IDs. This is followed by results from the misclassification analysis.

4.2.1 Top Level Category Results

The results of the classification on top level categories are further broken down into the classifier and filter combination used.

KNN Classifier with Category Filters

Figure 8 shows the overall average metrics of repeated runs of the KNN classifier on filtered top level categories. The metrics provided are the averages of: 1) Overall Accuracy, 2) F1 Score, 3) AUR-ROC Score and 4) the Category Balanced Accuracy. As can be seen, across multiple classification runs, the CLAP model appears to perform marginally better than the LAION-CLAP model. Also to be noted is the observation that the Category Balanced Accuracy is always lower than the Overall Accuracy across all feature extractors. Figures 9 and 10 display the category-wise accuracy and confusion matrix of the CLAP model respectively. The category-wise accuracies of the remaining feature extractor models as well as the confusion matrices can be found in Appendix A.1.1

KNN Classifier without Category Filters

The overall average metrics without any category filters applied show a slight reduction in the classification performance as can be seen in Figure 11. The CLAP

model continues to perform the best irrespective of the application of category filters. The category-wise accuracy and confusion matrix of CLAP under these conditions is shown in Figures 12 and 13 respectively. Further plots of the remaining models' category-wise accuracies, as well as the confusion matrices of all the feature extractor models under these experimental conditions can be found in Appendix A.2.1.

MLP Classifier with Category Filters

Since the previous experiments clearly demonstrated that the CLAP and LAION-CLAP models significantly outperform the FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models, the results for FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models are omitted from further discussion in top level categories for the sake of brevity, as they are no longer pertinent to the analysis of classification performance. The remaining results will instead focus on the CLAP and LAION-CLAP models, the classifier models, and the effects of filters and category levels.

Figure 14 presents the overall average metrics of 30 runs of the MLP classifier on filtered top level categories, with different train-validation sets used for each run. The two feature extractor models perform similarly, though the CLAP model holds a slight edge over LAION-CLAP. As observed previously, the Category Balanced Accuracy remains lower than the Overall Accuracy, and both models achieve a very high AUC-ROC score. The category-wise accuracies and confusion matrices of the two models are presented in Appendix A.3.1.

MLP Classifier without Category Filters

It can be observed in Figure 15 that the performance of the Overall Accuracy, F1 Score and Category Balanced Accuracy have reduced without category filters being applied, albeit only to a small extent. The AUR-ROC score, however has only dropped negligibly. The plots of the category-wise accuracies and the confusion matrices of the two models can be found in Appendix A.4.1

Figure 8: Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Filtered KNN Classifier

Figure 9: Category-wise TLC Accuracies of CLAP with Filtered KNN Classifier

Figure 10: Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Filtered KNN Classifier

Figure 11: Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Unfiltered KNN Classifier

Figure 12: Category-wise TLC Accuracies of CLAP with Unfiltered KNN Classifier

Figure 13: Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Unfiltered KNN Classifier

Figure 14: Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Filtered MLP Classifier

Figure 15: Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Unfiltered MLP Classifier

4.2.2 Category ID Level Results

The classification of the category IDs are also divided into the combination of classifier and filter used. Similar to the results of the top level categories, the KNN classifier performance across all four feature extractors are reported. However, thereafter, the results for the MLP classifier are restricted to the two best performing models: CLAP and LAION-CLAP. The main findings with respect to the metrics of Overall Accuracy, Category Balanced Accuracy, F1 Score and AUR-ROC Score are reported within this section.

KNN Classifier with Category Filters

Figure 16 shows the same trend with respect to the classification performance across the feature extractors. It is to be noted that while the performance of the filtered category ID classification metrics is worse than that with filtered top level categories, it does outperform the unfiltered top level categories by a small amount. Further results can be found in Appendix A.5.1.

KNN Classifier without Category Filters

From Figure 17, it is observed that the absence of category filters slightly diminishes classification performance at the category ID level, mirroring the trend observed in top-level category classification. Although the reduction is minor, the consistent superior performance of filtered categories compared to unfiltered ones across experiments is clear. Plots of confusion matrices are available in Appendix A.5.2

MLP Classifier with Category Filters

It can be observed in Figure 18 that the MLP classifier scores lower in the metrics of accuracy and F1 score as compared to the KNN classifier, but performs better at the AUR-ROC score. This pattern has been consistently observed throughout the experiments and will be further analyzed in the Discussion section. The confusion matrices of the two models are provided in Appendix A.6.1.

Figure 16: Overall Metrics of Filtered Category IDs; KNN Classifier

Figure 17: Overall Metrics of Unfiltered Category IDs; KNN Classifier

MLP Classifier without Category Filters

Figure 19 shows a further reduction in accuracy and F1 scores by removing category filters. The AUR-ROC score, however remains almost the same as the category filtered version of this combination. Further plots of confusion matrices can be found in Appendix A.6.2.

4.2.3 Misclassification Analysis

The misclassification analysis was conducted as detailed in section 3.2.3 through the manual listening and marking of sensible classifications. Since CLAP was the best performing model across all experiments, and since the MLP classifier produced the highest AUR-ROC score, the misclassification analysis was conducted with this extractor-classifier model on filtered top level categories.

Among the 100 misclassified validation audio files randomly selected from this extractor-classifier-filter combination, the predicted categories of 63 files were deemed sensible from a sound design perspective; in other words, these sounds closely matched what could be expected from their predicted categories. This number was then used to estimate the accuracy of sensible misclassifications for this model. With an overall average accuracy of 0.631, it means that 37 out of 100 audio files are not predicted as the ground truth. Given that 63 percent of the misclassifications are sensible, 23 out of these 37 misclassified files can be considered reasonably classified. Therefore, a total of 86 out of 100 audio files can be assumed to be sensibly classified by this combination model, suggesting that the model's effective accuracy could be around 0.86.

CLAP MLP Filtered Top Level Category Classification:

Overall Avg. Acc. = 0.631

Sensible misclassifications = 63 out of 100 = 63%

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Estimated Adjusted Overall Accuracy} &= 0.631 + [63\% \text{ of } (1 - 0.631)] \\ &= \mathbf{0.861} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 18: Overall Metrics of Filtered Category IDs; MLP Classifier

Figure 19: Overall Metrics of Unfiltered Category IDs; MLP Classifier

4.3 Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset

From the experiments conducted in Level 2, the best performing variables were selected for the classification evaluation on the entire dataset:

1. Feature Extractor: CLAP
2. Classifier (Based on AUR-ROC score): MLP
3. Category Level: Top Level Category

Although the filtered categories performed better across experiments in Level 2, unfiltered top level categories were taken for the experiments at this level 3; the reasoning for which is discussed later in the Discussion section. Therefore, the combination model used for Level 3 experiments is the CLAP extractor using a MLP classifier with unfiltered top level categories.

The overall average metrics of this combination model is given in Figure 20. The model's performance is slightly better in all metrics in comparison to the same CLAP model which classified the subset of the dataset as can be seen in Figure 15. The model has an Average Category Balanced Accuracy of 0.564. In order to understand the variability of this metric over the 30 iterations of the classification with different train-validation sets, a boxplot of the Category Balanced Accuracy at each iteration was computed. This boxplot is displayed in Figure 21.

The category-wise accuracy of the model is given in Figure 22. It is worth noting that the category-wise accuracy of the 'CHEMICALS' category has fallen considerably in comparison to its value in the same model, with the subset of the dataset in the Level 2 experiments. Figure 23 displays the confusion matrix of the model.

Figure 20: Overall Metrics of Level 3 Experiments

Figure 21: Boxplot of Category Balanced Accuracy

Figure 22: Category-wise Accuracy of the Model

Figure 23: Confusion Matrix of the Model

Misclassification Analysis

Following the methodology determined in Section 3.3.2, the ‘MOVEMENT’ category was selected in order to conduct a tSNE-based analysis, owing to its low average accuracy in the classification process. Figure 24 shows that out of an average 43 occurrences of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category in the validation set, an average of 29.03 of those occurrences are misclassified. ‘AMBIENCE’ was the category that it was most misclassified as, at an average of 9.6 misclassifications in an iteration, and ‘CROWDS’ was the next most misclassified category at an average of 7.1 misclassifications in an iteration.

Figure 24: Top 3 Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category

A tSNE scatter plot, as shown in Figure 25 was computed using the embeddings of the three categories: ‘MOVEMENT’, ‘AMBIENCE’ and ‘CROWDS’, marked in black, blue and green respectively. The audio files that belong to the ground truth category of ‘MOVEMENT’ but were misclassified as either ‘AMBIENCE’ or ‘CROWDS’ are marked in red. The tSNE plot shows a clear overlap area of embedding regions of the three categories, which is where the misclassifications are occurring.

Figure 25: tSNE Plot of the Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category

Chapter 5

Discussion

In this section, the results presented in the previous chapter will be discussed in detail in order to draw up reasonable conclusions regarding the classification process and the relevance of misclassifications from the sound design use-case perspective. This section is broken down into three sections in order to separately analyse each level of experimentation that was conducted.

5.1 Level 1: Initial Evaluation on Dataset Subset

The first level of experiments were conducted to get a general idea of the performance of the different feature extractors and classifiers that were being studied.

Figures 4, 5 and 6 show an advantage of semantic based feature extractor models - CLAP and LAION-CLAP - over the FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models. At the same time, the MLP classifier appears to perform better with the FSD-SINET and Freesound Extractor models, and especially better with the AUR-ROC scores across all classifiers. The confusion matrices of the extractor models in Figure 7 visually corroborate the pattern observed in the accuracy metric across the extractors: CLAP and LAION-CLAP display a strong diagonal, which progressively weakens through FSD-SINET and is weakest in the Freesound Extractor.

However, as the results from this level are based off a single run of the classification

process on the dataset’s subset, it considers only a single train-validation split of the data, and need not be representative of it’s average performance over repeated classification runs. For this reason, a thorough analysis of the results will be provided in the next section when the Level 2 experiments confirm the patterns that are observed here.

5.2 Level 2: Multiple Classification Runs

The classification process was run multiple times using both KNN and MLP classifiers at two category levels, yielding results that allowed for a comprehensive analysis. This analysis helped confirm patterns observed in the level 1 experiments and also led to additional conclusions.

5.2.1 KNN vs MLP

Table 4 details the metrics of CLAP’s performance on filtered top level categories with a KNN and MLP classifier. The KNN classifier slightly outperforms the MLP classifier in overall accuracy, category balanced accuracy, and F1 score, while the MLP significantly excels in the AUC-ROC score. This pattern is consistent across all feature extractor models and is also observed in category ID level classification, as shown in the figures in Section 4.2.

Table 4: KNN vs MLP Top Level Category Performance: CLAP

Classifier	Overall Acc.	Balanced Acc.	F1 Score	AUR-ROC
KNN	0.659	0.623	0.646	0.887
MLP	0.631	0.597	0.627	0.97

The reason for the KNN classifier performing better at accuracy and F1 score related metrics can be attributed to a few reasons. Firstly, it is important to take note of a few factors of the dataset itself that can contribute to such metrics:

1. The dataset is quite imbalanced. This means that the classifiers receive more data points for training from certain categories while receiving far fewer data

points from other categories, already creating a bias in performance between the two categories.

2. Certain categories might have little variance in the features of the audios within them, while other categories might have a large variance. This is slightly related to how broad the definition of a category is. For example, the category, 'BEEPS', is expected to have a smaller feature variance amongst its audio files than the category, 'AMBIENCE', which could contain audio files of ambiences from peaceful countrysides to noisy city streets from around the world, whose features are clearly quite varied from each other. This results in the data points of low variance categories to be densely clustered in the embedding space, while those of high variance categories are sparsely distributed across the space.
3. Certain categories can also be understood as subsets or overlapping sets of other categories. For example, water being poured into a glass can either be annotated during the dataset creation process as the category, 'WATER' or the category, 'FOOD & DRINKS'. This results in such categories either living inside, or sharing the embedding space regions of other categories. As the two classifiers in this study work on decision boundary based methods, such cases can make the classification process extremely complicated and error-prone for the classifiers. However, significantly, these are exactly those areas where this study expects to find sensible misclassifications, and will be discussed in further detail later in this chapter.

By keeping the above points in mind, it will now be easier to reason the difference in performance between the KNN and MLP classifiers.

KNN classifiers make decision boundaries for classification based on polling the data points in the local region. Additionally, a small number for k - which is the case in this study ($k = 3$) - further emphasizes the weight of local regions upon the classification decision, as it does not consider dispersed points that might be further away in the region. This would mean that a KNN classifier would tend to tightly

fit to the training data by creating highly irregular boundaries that closely follow the contour of the category’s embedding region. If the category has low variance, i.e. densely clustered, the accuracy of the KNN classifier would be quite high with the validation data, especially if the validation data points are very similar to the training data. However, if the category has a higher variance, then it will not be able to capture the dispersed data points that fall outside a more densely packed area of the category space. The MLP classifier, on the other hand, does not rely as much on local variations in order to form its decision boundaries between categories, but looks at a more global picture of the data. This results in a slightly looser decision boundary that can accommodate variations in features, which results in the accuracy of the classifier being sacrificed for the sake of better generalisation. This can be confirmed by looking at category-wise accuracies instead of the overall accuracy of the classifier. The category-wise accuracy of ‘AMBIENCE’ - a category with a high feature variance - in the KNN classifier as seen in Figure 12 is approximately 0.2. The same value in the MLP classifier is approximately 0.25 as can be observed in Figure 41. This behaviour can be extended and attributed to the category balanced accuracy and the F1 score as well.

Interestingly, the KNN classifier showing a better overall accuracy can therefore hint at the fact that a larger proportion of the data points in the dataset are tightly clustered in the embedding space. Similarly, by observing that the the CLAP and LAION-CLAP feature extractors regularly perform with a higher accuracy score, it can be argued that combined semantic and acoustic embedding spaces are better structured and distributed as compared to the other two embedding spaces, thereby making it easier for classifiers to make decision boundaries between categories.

The MLP classifier, however, clearly outperforms the KNN classifier at the AUR-ROC score in all cases. The AUR-ROC score aims to indicate how well a classifier is able to distinguish between categories, i.e. how well it is able to separate the positive and negative classes. Note that this is different from how accuracy is measured. Specifically, the AUR-ROC score measures the probability that the classifier will rank a randomly chosen positive instance higher than a randomly chosen negative

instance. Due to the MLP’s classifier’s global approach to form smoother decision boundaries, it is able to better capture the underlying structure of the data, which results in significantly higher AUR-ROC scores, at the cost of accuracy.

5.2.2 Effect of Category Filters

Table 5 below shows that applying category filters has a positive effect on all of the performance metrics in the classification task, thereby giving weight to the assumption that neglecting categories that are too vaguely defined would be advantageous.

Table 5: Filtered vs Unfiltered Top Level Category Performance: CLAP

Filter	Overall Acc.	Balanced Acc.	F1 Score	AUR-ROC
Yes	0.631	0.597	0.627	0.97
No	0.564	0.527	0.559	0.961

However, there are a few caveats to this assumption. Firstly, removing categories from the dataset reduces the complexity of the classification task, as the classifier has fewer categories to differentiate. For example, it is easier for a classifier to distinguish between two classes in an embedding space than between ten, particularly when there is overlap between classes. This reduction in complexity can inherently lead to higher accuracy scores. Additionally, class imbalance can also influence the accuracy metric. For instance, if a category is particularly challenging for the model to classify and contains an overwhelmingly large number of samples, removing this category could significantly boost the classifier’s accuracy. Conversely, eliminating an easy-to-classify category could result in a decrease in overall accuracy. There are examples of both such categories in the Pro Sound Effects dataset. ‘OBJECTS’ was one of the categories selected to be filtered out due to the lack of specificity in its definition. It contains 88 sounds in the dataset subset used in Level 2 experiments, and CLAP’s category-wise accuracy of ‘OBJECTS’ with an MLP classifier is just above 0.2. Removing this category would effectively undo approximately 70 misclassifications that had occurred in the classification process, and therefore bring up the accuracy of the classifier. On the other hand, the ‘ARCHIVED’ category has the highest of

all category-wise accuracies at over 0.9, and contains 100 sound files in the dataset subset. Filtering out this class would therefore ignore over 90 correct classifications in the accuracy score, leading to a drop in the overall accuracy of the classifier. The category balanced accuracy was introduced as a performance metric to partially address this class imbalance. However, this metric too, continued to follow the same trend as the overall accuracy as other experiment variables were adjusted.

5.2.3 Effect of Category Levels

Table 6 displays the comparative performance metrics between Top Level Categories (TLC) and Category ID (CatID). The top level categories produce better accuracy and f1 scores than category IDs do. This could be attributed to the fact that the category ID is a combination of the top level category with a sub category, and often times, there is only an extremely tiny distinguishing factor between the sub categories. This would tend to place the embeddings of the two category IDs close to each other or even overlap each other in the embedding space, leading to confusion in the classification task for the classifier. Additionally, since the category IDs are far more specific categories that sub-divide the top level category, they also tend to have fewer samples within the category to train the classifier with. In many cases, there are category IDs that only have a single audio file in them. For the sake of this study, category IDs that had fewer than 10 audio files were not considered for the classification task.

Table 6: TLC vs CatID Performance: CLAP

Category	Overall Acc.	Balanced Acc.	F1 Score	AUR-ROC
TLC	0.564	0.527	0.559	0.961
CatID	0.541	0.462	0.528	0.972

It is interesting to note that the Category ID produces a better AUR-ROC score than the Top Level Category. The reason for this could be that there are an overwhelming majority of Category Ids which are distinctly well structured in the embedding space to allow for the MLP classifier to draw accurate boundaries between

the sub-categories in the top level category's embedding region. At this point it is worth mentioning that this is not the case with a KNN classifier. The AUR-ROC score of the KNN classifier with top level categories is 0.861 (Figure 11), which in contrast to the performance of the MLP classifier, reduces to 0.854 with category IDs (Figure 17). This indeed goes to show how the MLP continues to outperform the KNN at distinguishing between classes.

5.2.4 Category ID Confusion Matrices

Extending the analysis of the category IDs a step further, Figure 26 shows an example of an interesting occurrence in all the confusion matrices of classifications at the category ID level. Firstly, as there are over 115 category IDs in this classification task, it is to be noted that the category ID names are not labelled on the x and y axes of the plot due to space restrictions. The category IDs are however, sorted in alphabetical order.

Figure 26: Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Filtered Category IDs

The regions circled in red can be seen as ‘regions of confusion’, where an audio file is mistakenly classified as a neighbouring category. Knowing that the category IDs are sorted alphabetically, and that category IDs often share a top level category (for example, CLOTHMvmt and CLOTHFlap share the ‘CLOTH’ top level category), it becomes apparent that these regions of confusion occur between category IDs with the same parent category. This is logical, as the model might easily confuse CLOTHMvmt with CLOTHFlap, and vice versa, possibly due to overlapping embedding regions for these category IDs. This also explains why top-level categories tend to perform better in accuracy and F1 score metrics compared to category IDs.

5.2.5 Misclassification Analysis

The misclassification analysis was conducted by manually listening to the audio files that were misclassified, and looking at their predicted category. This exercise brought out a few interesting observations that are summarised here.

As pointed out in Section 4.2.3, there are a large number of misclassifications that make sense in terms of their predicted category, from a sound design perspective. The reasoning for why they make sense can be divided into three kinds of arguments which are explained below using examples.

1. **Misclassifications where the predicted category is actually present in the file name or sub-category name:**

For example, the audio file named ‘TOONImpt_Comic-Weapon-Blast-**Liquid**-Burst-Squirt-Drip-21’ was classified as ‘LIQUID & MUD’ instead of being classified as ‘CARTOON’.

Similarly, ‘TOY**Mech**_Toy-Wind-Up-Monkey-Load-Release-01’ was classified as ‘MECHANICAL’; the ‘Mech’ in ‘TOYMech’ referring to Mechanical as a sub-category. Additionally, a manual listen of these two files also acoustically confirmed the sensibility of the predicted class.

2. **Misclassifications where the predicted category is semantically and/or acoustically similar to the ground truth top level category:**

The audio file ‘ICEFric_Ice-Scrape’ was classified as ‘SNOW’ by the CLAP classifier, instead of the ground truth - ‘ICE’. The semantic information that the embeddings contain could have played a role in deeming ‘SNOW’ to be semantically similar and close to ‘ICE’. Acoustically too, the audio file demonstrated the quality of an impact on crunchy snow. Another similar example is the misclassification of ‘CERMCrsh_Ceramic-Debris-Mvs-Tinkle-Subtle’ as ‘GLASS’ instead of ‘CERAMIC’.

An example of a misclassification that showed only an acoustic similarity to the predicted category was the prediction of the audio file ‘GOREFlesh_Zombie-Flesh-Stab’ as ‘SNOW’, instead of ‘GORE’. While SNOW and GORE are not in each other’s semantic neighbourhoods, the acoustic quality of the audio file did indeed convey the sense of a pick-axe’s impact into snow. At this point it is interesting to think of the practical usefulness of such misclassifications by deconstructing them into suggesting possible objects and actions to Foley artists to recreate real sounds; in this case, the sound of a pick-axe cutting into snow could possibly be used as the sound of a zombie being stabbed in its flesh!

3. Misclassifications where the predicted category better describes the sound than the annotated ground truth category:

Due to the subjective nature of how every human being perceives and classifies a sound, there is always the possibility that the ground truth annotation of a sound in a dataset might not best describe the category that it could belong to.

The audio file ‘TRNSbwy_Subway-Station-Los-Angeles-Air-Hum-Voices’ is a recording of passengers chatting while waiting for a train in a subway station while other passengers move around in the background. The annotated ground truth category for this file is ‘TRAINS’. While the recording does take place at a train subway station, it can be argued that the recording is not taking place inside the train itself, and can also be argued that there is no sound present in the recording that is emitted from a train. The predicted category

for this audio file was ‘CROWDS’, which offers a far more sensible suggestion of the category the audio file could belong to, from both a logical and acoustic standpoint.

It is on the basis of such considerations as above that a revised accuracy is suggested, as detailed in Section 4.2.3. This revision presents a more accurate picture of the classifier’s ability to make sensible predictions from a sound design perspective.

5.3 Level 3: Evaluation on the Entire Dataset

The final phase of the experimental analysis involved conducting thirty classification runs using CLAP embeddings with an unfiltered top-level category MLP classifier. The results from this phase largely confirmed the performance metrics observed under similar conditions with a subset of the dataset in the level 2 experiments. However, it also revealed a few intriguing observations. Both aspects are discussed in this section.

5.3.1 Comparison with Level 2 Metrics

Table 7 compares the classification performance between the subset and the entire dataset. While including the entire dataset in the process maintains the characteristic performance trends seen with the subset, it also results in an overall improvement in performance. This outcome is expected, as the larger dataset provides significantly more training data. However, it’s worth noting that an approximately 18-fold increase in the amount of training and validation data results in only a 0.04 improvement in accuracy and F1 scores, and a 0.01 increase in AUC-ROC performance. This suggests that classification performance approaches an asymptote relatively quickly, even with a limited amount of data, such as a subset.

Table 7: Subset vs Entire Dataset Performance

Dataset	Overall Acc.	Balanced Acc.	F1 Score	AUR-ROC
Subset	0.564	0.527	0.559	0.961
Entire	0.6	0.564	0.599	0.971

5.3.2 Drop in ‘CHEMICALS’ performance

However, in contrast to the general asymptotic behaviour of the classifier’s performance with increasing data availability, the category-wise accuracy of the ‘CHEMICALS’ category shows a sudden drop in accuracy from being above 0.7 in level 2 experiments (Figure 41) to falling below 0.4 in level 3 experiments (Figure 22), despite a large increase in data points for the purpose of training. This would require a thorough and detailed analysis of the composition of the audio files in the category in the subset vs. the entire dataset which is beyond the scope of this thesis. However, there could be a couple of simple reasons for this behaviour.

Firstly, if the subset of the dataset was created by selecting the first n sorted samples from each category, it’s possible that these samples were acoustically very similar to one another (e.g., multiple recordings of the same sound with slight variations, as is common in sound libraries). This similarity could lead to a dense clustering in the embedding space, making it easier for the classifier to categorize them. When the entire category was sampled for the level 3 experiments, the remaining sounds in the category might have exhibited much greater variance than the subset, making them harder for the classifier to predict accurately.

Secondly, using the entire dataset in the classification process would likely increase the overlap between neighboring categories as the number of samples in each category grows, making it more challenging for the classifiers to establish accurate decision boundaries.

5.3.3 Consistency of Classification over Multiple Runs

Considering that the entire dataset is quite huge, it was important to observe the variance in the performance across multiple runs, that is, with different train and validation data splits. The reasoning behind this is to verify if the make-up of the training set can widely affect the accuracy of the classifier. To measure this, the average category balanced accuracy was taken for each of the thirty runs of the classification process and a boxplot was computed, as shown in Figure 27

Figure 27: Boxplot of Avg. Category Balanced Accuracy across Multiple Runs

The boxplot displays a narrow interquartile range of just under 0.01, with the minimum and maximum values spanning a difference of 0.03. There is only one outlier, which is 0.025 away from the mean. This indicates that multiple runs of the classification process yield consistent performance with minimal variation.

5.3.4 tSNE Analysis

A tSNE plot was computed using three categories: ‘MOVEMENT’, ‘AMBIENCE’ and ‘CROWDS’, where ‘MOVEMENT’ was the ground truth category to be predicted. The audio files that were misclassified as the other two categories were plotted separately in red. The plot showed that the majority of the misclassifications happened in a region of dense category overlaps. This region is circled in yellow in Figure 28 below.

Figure 28: tSNE Plot of the Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category

While it shouldn't come as a surprise that the misclassifications occur in a dense region of category overlaps, as it inherently becomes difficult for classifiers to make accurate decision boundaries there, there are, however, a few other observations of interest.

Firstly, it can be seen that the 'AMBIENCE' and 'MOVEMENT' categories are quite dispersed, hinting at the variance in the acoustic and semantic features of the audio files present within them. The 'AMBIENCE' category, however, contains a few regions of local, dense clusters of its audio files. On the other hand, the 'CROWDS' category is a lot more tightly clustered within a small region. Their corresponding distribution in the embedding space should have a direct affect on their respective category-wise accuracies, which can be confirmed from Table 8 below.

Table 8: Category-wise Accuracy Scores

Category	'MOVEMENT'	'AMBIENCE'	'CROWDS'
Accuracy	0.325	0.548	0.770

Secondly, for the categories 'AMBIENCE' and 'CROWDS', the region of overlap does not occur close to what can be assumed to be their respective cluster's centroid. But it occurs in what can be understood as their 'border regions'. These overlapping border regions appear to represent an area of high ambiguity where a sound residing within can possibly be sensibly classified as either of the categories that are overlapping each other in that region. The 'MOVEMENT' category itself is quite sparsely populated, but shows a slightly larger level of concentration in this overlapping region (circled in yellow in the figure above). It is therefore, not surprising to find most of the misclassifications to occur in this region. It is also worth noting that an overwhelmingly large number of the misclassifications in this example had the word 'crowd' within the audio file name, thereby strengthening the claim that these misclassifications are sensible.

5.4 Future Work

The study conducted in this Master Thesis is an initial analysis of meaningful misclassifications in the process of automatic sound classification. The aim was to lay a foundation of observations and patterns upon which further detailed studies can be built. A few such possibilities for future work are listed below:

1. The tSNE plot can be the starting point for a deeper investigation into how sounds in overlapping border regions can practically be categorised/tagged with multiple categories, to allow for a more robust interpretation of audio files, which includes the possibility that a sound can be equally and sensibly perceived to belong to multiple categories. Such a study would require a larger scale listening experiment that brings in the perspective of a diverse population when given sounds from such regions to classify or verify.
2. At a more fundamental level, it would be important to verify the misclassifications of a classifier through a large subjective listening experiment where participants from a diverse population are made to rank/validate the predictions of these classifiers in order to procure a more justifiable and robust accuracy estimation. The manually estimated overall accuracy that was developed in this study is based only on the first author's subjective listening experience, and can therefore only be taken as a proof of concept, which would thereafter require a rigorous scientific approach to back its claim.
3. Given that such studies and experiments depend on well-annotated datasets, it is crucial to establish clear guidelines for human annotators to ensure consistency in labeling ground truth. It would be intriguing to investigate whether existing datasets reveal patterns in how certain sounds are categorized. For example, are ambient sounds typically classified by both their source and location? Or are sports sounds categorized by the object and the action that produces the sound? If consistent patterns emerge across multiple datasets, their potential as guidelines could be explored, with further validation through both machine-made classifications and sensible misclassifications.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The research conducted in this thesis presents a novel approach to automatic sound classification, emphasizing the significance of misclassifications, particularly within the context of sound design. The study tested various feature extraction methods and classifiers, demonstrating that models incorporating both semantic and acoustic features significantly improve classification performance. The key finding is that many misclassifications, typically viewed as errors, can be acoustically meaningful and should be recognized as such, particularly in creative fields like sound design.

The use of the Universal Category System (UCS) provided a robust framework for categorizing sounds, but it also highlighted the limitations of traditional single-label classification approaches. By proposing that multiple categories could be assigned to a single sound based on its acoustic properties and context, this thesis opens up new avenues for enhancing the flexibility and effectiveness of sound classification systems.

Future work should focus on developing multi-label classification systems that better capture the nuances of sound perception and use. Incorporating user feedback into sound categorization could further enhance the accuracy and relevance of automatic classification systems, making them more adaptable to diverse applications. These advancements have the potential to create more sophisticated systems that are well-suited to the complexities of real-world audio environments.

List of Figures

1	Overview of the UrbanSound Taxonomy	18
2	First Two Layers of the Audioset Ontology	19
3	Example of Universal Category System’s Taxonomical Structure . . .	21
4	Classification Accuracy of each Feature Extractor and Classifier . . .	36
5	Classification F1 Score of each Feature Extractor and Classifier	37
6	Classification AUR-ROC Score of each Feature Extractor and Classifier	37
7	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a MLP Classifier.	38
8	Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Filtered KNN Classifier	41
9	Category-wise TLC Accuracies of CLAP with Filtered KNN Classifier	41
10	Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Filtered KNN Classifier	42
11	Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Unfiltered KNN Classifier	42
12	Category-wise TLC Accuracies of CLAP with Unfiltered KNN Classifier	43
13	Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Unfiltered KNN Classifier	43
14	Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Filtered MLP Classifier	44
15	Overall Metrics of Top Level Category (TLC) Unfiltered MLP Classifier	44
16	Overall Metrics of Filtered Category IDs; KNN Classifier	46
17	Overall Metrics of Unfiltered Category IDs; KNN Classifier	46
18	Overall Metrics of Filtered Category IDs; MLP Classifier	48
19	Overall Metrics of Unfiltered Category IDs; MLP Classifier	48
20	Overall Metrics of Level 3 Experiments	50
21	Boxplot of Category Balanced Accuracy	50
22	Category-wise Accuracy of the Model	51
23	Confusion Matrix of the Model	51

24	Top 3 Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category	52
25	tSNE Plot of the Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category . .	53
26	Confusion Matrix of CLAP with Filtered Category IDs	60
27	Boxplot of Avg. Category Balanced Accuracy across Multiple Runs .	65
28	tSNE Plot of the Misclassifications of the ‘MOVEMENT’ category . .	66
29	Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of LAION-CLAP	80
30	Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of FSD-SINET	81
31	Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of Freesound Extractor .	81
32	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Filtered)	82
33	Unfiltered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of LAION-CLAP	83
34	Unfiltered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of FSD-SINET	83
35	Unfiltered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of Freesound Extractor	84
36	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Unfiltered)	84
37	Filtered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of CLAP	85
38	Filtered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of LAION-CLAP	85
39	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Filtered)	86
40	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Unfiltered)	86
41	Unfiltered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of CLAP	87
42	Unfiltered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of LAION-CLAP	87
43	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Filtered)	88
44	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Unfiltered)	89
45	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Filtered)	90

46	Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Unfiltered)	90
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List of Tables

1	Analysis of available embeddings	27
2	No. of top level categories and audio files with/without filtering . . .	30
3	No. of category IDs and audio files with/without filtering	32
4	KNN vs MLP Top Level Category Performance: CLAP	55
5	Filtered vs Unfiltered Top Level Category Performance: CLAP	58
6	TLC vs CatID Performance: CLAP	59
7	Subset vs Entire Dataset Performance	64
8	Category-wise Accuracy Scores	67

Bibliography

- [1] Mehrabani, M., Bangalore, S. & Stern, B. Personalized speech recognition for internet of things. In *2015 IEEE 2nd World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*, 369–374 (2015).
- [2] Rasmussen, J. H., Stowell, D. & Briefer, E. F. Sound evidence for biodiversity monitoring. *Science* **385**, 138–140 (2024). URL <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.adh2716>. <https://www.science.org/doi/pdf/10.1126/science.adh2716>.
- [3] Nanni, L. *et al.* Bird and whale species identification using sound images. *IET Computer Vision* **12**, 178–184 (2018).
- [4] Müller, J. *et al.* Soundscapes and deep learning enable tracking biodiversity recovery in tropical forests. *Nature Communications* **14**, 6191 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41693-w>.
- [5] Karthikeyan, J., Sreehari, S., Koshy, J. R. & Kavitha, K. Live acoustic monitoring of forests to detect illegal logging and animal activity. In *Advances in Computing and Network Communications: Proceedings of CoCoNet 2020, Volume 2*, 89–101 (Springer, 2021).
- [6] Bourouhou, A., Jilbab, A., Nacir, C. & Hammouch, A. Heart sounds classification for a medical diagnostic assistance. *International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering* **15** (2019).

- [7] Kuluozturk, M. *et al.* Dkpnet41: Directed knight pattern network-based cough sound classification model for automatic disease diagnosis. *Medical Engineering & Physics* **110**, 103870 (2022).
- [8] Kim, Y. *et al.* Respiratory sound classification for crackles, wheezes, and rhonchi in the clinical field using deep learning. *Scientific reports* **11**, 1–11 (2021).
- [9] peeters guillermo g. & reiss joshua d. a deep learning approach to sound classification for film audio post-production. *journal of the audio engineering society* (2020).
- [10] Helmholtz, H. L. F. *On the Sensations of Tone as a Physiological Basis for the Theory of Music*. Cambridge Library Collection - Music (Cambridge University Press, 2009), 3 edn.
- [11] Terhardt, E. Pitch, consonance, and harmony. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **55**, 1061–1069 (1974). URL <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1914648>. https://pubs.aip.org/asa/jasa/article-pdf/55/5/1061/18782235/1061_1_online.pdf.
- [12] Risset, J.-C. & Wessel, D. L. 5 - exploration of timbre by analysis and synthesis. In Deutsch, D. (ed.) *The Psychology of Music (Second Edition)*, Cognition and Perception, 113–169 (Academic Press, San Diego, 1999), second edition edn. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780122135644500068>.
- [13] Chowning, J. The synthesis of complex audio spectra by means of frequency modulation. *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society* J. Audio Eng. Soc. 21 (7), 526–534. (1973).
- [14] Wertheimer, M. Laws of organization in perceptual forms. *Psychologische Forschung* **4**, 301–350 (1923).
- [15] Rosch, E. Principles of categorization. In Collins, A. & Smith, E. E. (eds.) *Readings in Cognitive Science, a Perspective From Psychology and Artificial Intelligence*, 312–22 (Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, 1978).

- [16] Bregman, A. S. *Auditory Scene Analysis: The Perceptual Organization of Sound* (The MIT Press, 1990). URL <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/1486.001.0001>.
- [17] Ballas, J. Common factors in the identification of an assortment of brief everyday sounds. *Journal of experimental psychology. Human perception and performance* **19**, 250–67 (1993).
- [18] Bansal, A. & Garg, N. K. Environmental sound classification: A descriptive review of the literature. *Intelligent Systems with Applications* **16**, 200115 (2022). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667305322000539>.
- [19] Couvreur, C., Fontaine, V., Gaunard, P. & Mubikangiey, C. G. Automatic classification of environmental noise events by hidden markov models. *Applied Acoustics* **54**, 187–206 (1998). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0003682X97001059>.
- [20] Allegro Baumann, S., Büchler, M. & Launer, S. Automatic sound classification inspired by auditory scene analysis. *Proc European Conf Sig Proc (EURASIP)* (2000).
- [21] Lu, L. & Li, S. Content-based audio segmentation using support vector machines. *IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo, 2001* (2001).
- [22] Lin, C.-C., Chen, S.-H., Truong, T.-K. & Chang, Y. Audio classification and categorization based on wavelets and support vector machine. *IEEE Transactions on Speech and Audio Processing* **13**, 644–651 (2005).
- [23] Chen, L., Gunduz, S. & Ozsu, M. T. Mixed type audio classification with support vector machine. In *2006 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo*, 781–784 (2006).
- [24] Bahoura, M. & Pelletier, C. Respiratory sounds classification using cepstral analysis and gaussian mixture models. In *The 26th Annual International Con-*

- ference of the *IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, vol. 1, 9–12 (2004).
- [25] Roch, M. A., Soldevilla, M. S., Burtenshaw, J. C., Henderson, E. E. & Hildebrand, J. A. Gaussian mixture model classification of odontocetes in the Southern California Bight and the Gulf of California. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **121**, 1737–1748 (2007). URL <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2400663>. https://pubs.aip.org/asa/jasa/article-pdf/121/3/1737/13087578/1737_1_online.pdf.
- [26] Rajapakse, M. & Wyse, L. Generic audio classification using a hybrid model based on gmms and hmms. In *11th International Multimedia Modelling Conference*, 53–58 (2005).
- [27] Hershey, S. *et al.* Cnn architectures for large-scale audio classification. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 131–135 (2017).
- [28] Salamon, J. & Bello, J. P. Deep convolutional neural networks and data augmentation for environmental sound classification. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* **24**, 279–283 (2017).
- [29] Piczak, K. J. Environmental sound classification with convolutional neural networks. In *2015 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing (MLSP)*, 1–6 (2015).
- [30] Bae, S. H., Choi, I. K. & Kim, N. S. Acoustic scene classification using parallel combination of lstm and cnn. In *DCASE*, 11–15 (2016).
- [31] Bubashait, M. & Hewahi, N. Urban sound classification using dnn, cnn & lstm a comparative approach. In *2021 International Conference on Innovation and Intelligence for Informatics, Computing, and Technologies (3ICT)*, 46–50 (2021).

- [32] Bahmei, B., Birmingham, E. & Arzanpour, S. Cnn-rnn and data augmentation using deep convolutional generative adversarial network for environmental sound classification. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* **29**, 682–686 (2022).
- [33] Gong, Y., Chung, Y.-A. & Glass, J. Ast: Audio spectrogram transformer (2021). 2104.01778.
- [34] Chen, K. *et al.* Hts-at: A hierarchical token-semantic audio transformer for sound classification and detection. In *ICASSP 2022 - 2022 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 646–650 (2022).
- [35] Garofolo, J. *et al.* Timit acoustic-phonetic continuous speech corpus. *Linguistic Data Consortium* (1992).
- [36] Pearce, D. & Hirsch, H.-G. The aurora experimental framework for the performance evaluations of speech recognition systems under noisy condition. In *Proc. ICSLP*, vol. 4, 29–32 (2000).
- [37] Tzanetakis, G. & Cook, P. Musical genre classification of audio signals. *IEEE Transactions on Speech and Audio Processing* **10**, 293–302 (2002).
- [38] Salamon, J., Jacoby, C. & Bello, J. P. A dataset and taxonomy for urban sound research. *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM international conference on Multimedia* (2014). URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:207217115>.
- [39] Piczak, K. J. Esc: Dataset for environmental sound classification. In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, MM '15, 1015–1018 (Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2015). URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/2733373.2806390>.
- [40] Font, F. & Serra, X. Analysis of the folksonomy of freesound. In *Proceedings of the 2nd CompMusic Workshop*, 48–54 (2012).
- [41] Gemmeke, J. F. *et al.* Audio set: An ontology and human-labeled dataset for audio events. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 776–780 (2017).

- [42] Fonseca, E., Favory, X., Pons, J., Font, F. & Serra, X. FSD50K: an open dataset of human-labeled sound events. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* **30**, 829–852 (2022).
- [43] Fonseca, E., Ferraro, A. & Serra, X. Improving sound event classification by increasing shift invariance in convolutional neural networks (2021). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.00623>. 2107.00623.
- [44] Elizalde, B., Deshmukh, S., Ismail, M. A. & Wang, H. Clap: Learning audio concepts from natural language supervision (2022). 2206.04769.
- [45] Drossos, K., Lipping, S. & Virtanen, T. Clotho: An audio captioning dataset (2019). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.09387>. 1910.09387.
- [46] Kim, C. D., Kim, B., Lee, H. & Kim, G. AudioCaps: Generating captions for audios in the wild. In Burstein, J., Doran, C. & Solorio, T. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*, 119–132 (Association for Computational Linguistics, Minneapolis, Minnesota, 2019). URL <https://aclanthology.org/N19-1011>.
- [47] Martin Morato, I. & Mesaros, A. Diversity and bias in audio captioning datasets. In Font, F. *et al.* (eds.) *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events (DCASE 2021)*, 90–94 (2021). Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events ; Conference date: 15-11-2021 Through 19-11-2021.
- [48] Wu, Y. *et al.* Large-scale contrastive language-audio pretraining with feature fusion and keyword-to-caption augmentation (2024). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.06687>. 2211.06687.
- [49] Araz, R. O. *Semantic Sound Similarity with Deep Embeddings for Freesound*. Master’s thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8385275>.

Appendix A

Level 2 Experiment Plots

A.1 KNN Top Level Categories (Filtered)

A.1.1 Category-Wise Accuracy

Figure 29: Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of LAION-CLAP

Figure 30: Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of FSD-SINET

Figure 31: Filtered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of Freesound Extractor

A.1.2 Confusion Matrices

Figure 32: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Filtered)

Figure 35: Unfiltered TLC Category-wise KNN Accuracy of Freesound Extractor

A.2.2 Confusion Matrices

Figure 36: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Unfiltered)

A.3 MLP Top Level Categories (Filtered)

A.3.1 Category-Wise Accuracy

Figure 37: Filtered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of CLAP

Figure 38: Filtered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of LAION-CLAP

A.4.2 Category-Wise Accuracy

Figure 41: Unfiltered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of CLAP

Figure 42: Unfiltered TLC Category-wise MLP Accuracy of LAION-CLAP

A.5 KNN Category ID Level Confusion Matrices

A.5.1 Filtered

Figure 43: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Filtered)

A.5.2 Unfiltered

Figure 44: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP, b) LAION-CLAP, c) FSD-SINET and d) Freesound Extractor with a KNN Classifier (Unfiltered)

A.6 MLP Category ID Level Confusion Matrices

A.6.1 Filtered

Figure 45: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Filtered)

A.6.2 Unfiltered

Figure 46: Confusion Matrices of a) CLAP and b) LAION-CLAP with a MLP Classifier (Unfiltered)